

"SIGNIFICANT CHANGES IN LEGAL EDUCATION THAT WILL SERVE THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FIELD"

Abdulaziz Ravshanov

Tashkent state university of law
Student of Jurisprudence: Public law faculty
abdulazizravshanov06@gmail.com

Muhammadali Shahriddinov

Specialized school №220 in Tashkent
shahriddinov.muhammadali24@gmail.com

Article history:	Abstract:
Received: 11 th September 2021	Today's democratic and legal reforms around the world require the training of highly qualified legal personnel who meet modern international standards and the implementation of well-thought-out reforms that define the form, style and idea of education in the field of "jurisprudence".
Accepted: 11 th October 2021	
Published: 27 th November 2021	

Key Words: Legal education, jurisprudence, law, legal staff.

INTRODUCTION

The ongoing democratic and legal reforms in all countries, including Uzbekistan, require the training of highly qualified legal personnel meeting modern international standards, as well as the implementation of well-thought-out reforms that define the form, style and idea of education in the field of "jurisprudence". In this context, the Presidential Decree "On Additional Measures to Radically Improve Legal Education and Science in the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted yesterday has led to highly positive changes in the field of legal training. [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to the decree, with the opening of law faculties in three more higher educational institutions of the country, namely Samarkand, Namangan and Termez state universities, priorities for further development of legal education and science have been identified [2]. At the same time, the Decree provides for the order of formation of orders for the training of legal personnel. According to this procedure, the need for current and future legal personnel will be taken into account in determining the parameters of admission to legal education institutions [3]. In turn, setting quotas based on the need for legal staff may be a solution to some of the problems associated with a shortage of legal staff, not only in the public sector but also in the private sector.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In particular, if we analyze the need for legal staff in the legal profession in the region, there are currently 217 lawyers in Andijan region, which is one lawyer for every 14,000 citizens. This indicates the high level of demand for legal personnel [4].

If we compare these figures with the situation in developed countries, we can understand the essence of the problem. In the United States, for example, there are 260 lawyers, in Italy 265, in Germany 510, in Azerbaijan 670, in the Netherlands 905, in France 1,500, and in Kazakhstan 4,000 [5].

Of course, the situation with the shortage of legal staff can be seen not only in the private sector, but also in the legal services of government agencies and organizations.

It is important to note that the responsibility for ensuring the rule of law and the rule of law in the activities of government agencies and organizations, prevention of violations and taking timely action on them is primarily assigned to the legal staff of these organizations. the lack of legal staff in this area can lead to a number of problems.

Currently, there are 220 legal service staff units in the province, which leads to long-term vacancies for existing legal units in the province due to a lack of qualified legal staff, in which case the legal service staff is vacant. it can also be observed that a number of shortcomings in labor and contractual relations in their activities are perpetrated by organizations that are constantly plagued by staff shortages [6].

Therefore, in this context, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan aims to improve the quality of legal training and create competition among the staff.

The decree also stipulates that persons with higher legal education, working in senior positions in the central office of public authorities and administration after 5 years of legal experience, on the recommendation of the first head of the relevant state body, without admission tests. can be admitted to evening education programs.

In addition, with the Decree from the 2020-2021 academic year in law schools:

- the number of non-specialty subjects will be reduced and the educational process will be organized using a credit-module system;
- tests will be conducted by the State Testing Center, and an additional admission procedure will be introduced on the basis of a differentiated payment contract;
- have a higher legal education, at least in law school;
- teachers and administrators who have worked for 3 years have the right to enter the master's program of Tashkent State University without entrance exams, with the obligation to work for at least 3 years in law schools.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that today's reforms in this area include not only higher education institutions, but also legal colleges, the promotion of innovative ideas and the training of promising legal personnel. At the same time, it is planned to organize paid training and other courses in law schools, which will help to achieve high results in raising the legal awareness and legal culture of citizens.

REFERENCES

1. <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4766>
2. <https://lex.uz/docs/-4802181>
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On additional measures to radically improve legal education and science in the Republic of Uzbekistan"
4. <https://www.lawyertys.com/uzbekistan-lawyers/andijan-lawyers>
5. law.cornell.edu/supremecourt/text/347/260
6. FINAL REPORT OF THE LEGAL SERVICES TASK TEAM: For consideration by the Minister of Justice and the Benchers of Law Society of Saskatchewan
https://www.lawsociety.sk.ca/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/107840-legal_services_task_team_report_august_14-_2018-1.pdf